

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM FOR ENSURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article is devoted to "Improving the mechanism for ensuring the development of gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan" and in this article the long-term strategy for the development of gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan is to ensure sustainable economic growth while preserving the country's rich culinary heritage and it should be emphasized that it includes a general and multifaceted approach to promote.

Keywords: gastronomic tourism, culinary heritage, modern culinary infrastructure, guide map.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена теме «Совершенствование механизма обеспечения развития гастрономического туризма в Узбекистане» и в данной статье долгосрочной стратегией развития гастрономического туризма в Узбекистане является обеспечение устойчивого экономического роста при сохранении богатого кулинарного наследия страны и следует подчеркнуть, что он включает в себя общий и многогранный подход к содействию.

Ключевые слова: гастрономический туризм, кулинарное наследие, современная кулинарная инфраструктура, дорожная карта.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola “O‘zbekistonda gastronomik turizmni rivojlanishini ta’minlash mexanizmini takomillashtirish”ga bag‘ishlangan va ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda gastronomik turizmni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha uzoq muddatli strategiya barqaror iqtisodiy o‘rinishni ta’minlash bilan birga mamlakatning boy oshpazlik merosini saqlash va uni targ‘ib qilishga qaratilgan umumiy va ko‘p qirrali yondashuvni o‘z ichiga olganini ta’kidlab o‘tish lozim.

Kalit so‘zlar: gastronomik turizm, pazandachilik merosi, zamonaviy pazandachilik infratuzilmasi, yo‘l xaritasi.

Tourism is one of the leading and most static sectors of the world economy. This trend is recognized as an economic phenomenon with rapid growth rates. In many countries, tourism plays an important role in generating gross income. Many factors have contributed to the emergence and development of gastronomic tourism in recent years.

A long-term strategy for the development of gastronomic tourism may include various directions to create an environment in which gastronomic tourism can make a significant contribution to the overall tourism industry of Uzbekistan.[2] The picture below shows the strategic directions for the development of gastronomic tourism.

Figure -1. Strategic directions for the development of gastronomic tourism

It is important to create a solid basis for documenting, preserving and promoting the diverse culinary heritage of Uzbekistan. Culinary heritage conservation in food tourism development includes preserving, documenting and promoting traditional foods, recipes, cooking methods and the cultural significance of local cuisines.[3] Key aspects of culinary heritage conservation in the context of food tourism include documentation of traditional recipes, culinary archives and libraries, oral histories and interviews, culinary kitchens and training programs, culinary festivals and events, culinary tourism routes, promotion of local ingredients, culinary museums and exhibitions, culinary stories and integration with media and educational institutions.[1]

First, promote a governance model that is transparent, participatory and offers leadership. To this end:

- development of a strategic plan for the development of gastronomic tourism - a medium- and long-term “Road Map”, a common and consensus-based vision among agents in accordance with this goal and the goals of Sustainable Development;
- creating a mutual gastronomic tourism value chain that includes agents from different sectors directly or indirectly related to gastronomy;
- creation of mechanisms for public-public, public-private and intersectoral cooperation, communication and partnership among the subjects of gastronomic tourism on a geographical basis;

- create tools that will allow the different agents in the field to participate, share common principles, strengthen planning, decision-making and reach consensus on the policies needed to achieve the desired scenario of gastronomic tourism;
- provide institutional leadership and sufficient resources (both economic and human) to implement the action programs required in the gastronomic tourism development strategy in Uzbekistan.

Secondly, take measures to improve the situation, environment, places and system of receiving gastronomic tourists. To this end:

- creation of facilities to improve the gastronomic heritage: museums, locations, gastronomic centers, etc.;
- development of programs aimed at strengthening the design and elements of signs and the aesthetic and thematic aspects of gastronomy for the interpretation of gastronomic heritage;
- organizing events that target different communities to celebrate their food traditions, encourage pride in their community and preserve their cultural identity;
- promotion of thematic and expanded gastronomic content in tourist information offices and points of the region.

In order to develop tourism in Uzbekistan, expand the system of serving tourists and create all conditions for them, funds are allocated for the construction of new tourist complexes, hotels, campsites and restaurants, bars. In such a picture, the development of tourism necessarily requires the development of public catering. Because all tourists, regardless of whether they are domestic or foreign, are required to use the restaurant business or catering chain. Otherwise, a person will have to carry all the food with him or cook it and eat it at home. But tourists do not have such opportunities, so they are forced to use public catering services, and the presence of these conditions allows tourism to harmoniously develop public catering.

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